

Use of slow-release fertilizers to reduce nitrification

G. K. Patro and B. C. Sahu, Orissa University of Agriculture and Technology Bhubaneswar, India

Rice land soils in Orissa are alternately submerged and drained, which encourages nitrification of applied fertilizers and

reduces to 30% crop recovery of fertilizer nitrogen. We studied the effect of slow-release nitrogen fertilizers on Ratna growth and yield at Bhubaneswar.

Soil was a sandy loam with pH 5.4 and 756.4 kg N, 26.5 kg P, and 181.4 kg K/ha. Nitrogen was applied as isobutylidene diurea (BDU), AM fertilizer, lac-coated urea, and as urea mixed with karanj cake (*Pongamia pinnata*), a local-

ly available, low-cost forest product suitable for mechanical blending with urea. Karanj contains 4% N, 0.79% P, and 1.3% K and retards nitrification.

The number of effective tillers per hill indicated the beneficial effect of slow-release nitrogen fertilizers (see table). Applying 100 kg N/ha as lac-coated urea or karanj cake-coated urea produced almost as many effective tillers/hill as 100 kg urea N/ha.

Maximum plant height was produced with karanj cake-coated urea, closely followed by lac-coated urea and 16-10-14 IBDU (see table).

Panicle length was greater for all slow-release nitrogen fertilizers at 100 kg N/ha. As urea application without slow-release treatment decreased, average panicle length declined. The control treatment had shortest panicles.

Lac-coated urea produced best grain filling and highest weight, followed by karanj cake-coated urea.

Lac-coated urea produced maximum grain yield of 5.1 t/ha, followed closely by karanj cake-coated urea. Nitrogen at 100 kg/ha applied as lac-coated or karanj cake-coated urea produced significantly better rice growth and yield than 200 kg N/ha applied as ordinary urea. □

Effect of slow-release nitrogen fertilizers and urea on rice growth and yield, Bhubaneswar, India. ^a

Treatment	Growth attributes		Yield attributes			Grain yield (t/ha)
	Tillers/hill	Height (cm)	Panicle length (cm)	1000-grain wt (g)	Filled grains (no./panicle)	
Urea 50 kg N/ha	6	62	20	27	56	3.1
Urea 100 kg N/ha	7	63	21	28	61	3.9
Urea 150 kg N/ha	7	64	22	28	65	4.2
Urea 200 kg N/ha	7	65	23	28	69	4.7
Sulfur-coated urea (S ₁) (100 kg N/ha)	8	65	24	29	70	4.8
Sulfur-coated urea (S ₂) (100 kg N/ha)	7	64	23	28	69	4.7
IBDU (10-10-10) (100 kg N/ha)	7	65	24	29	70	4.9
IBDU (16-10-14) (100 kg N/ha)	8	69	24	29	70	4.9
Lac-coated urea (100 kg N/ha)	8	70	25	29	72	5.0
AM (100 kg N/ha)	7	65	29	28	69	4.9
Karanj (100 kg N/ha)	8	70	24	29	71	5.1
Control	5	52	19	22	55	3.1
CD (0.05)	0.99	2.46	0.70	1.46	2.31	0.15

^aAll treatments received a basal application of 18 kg P and 33 kg K/ha.

Effect of blue-green algae and nitrogen levels on rice yields

G. Ram and M. K. Misra, J. N. Krishi Vishwa Vidyalaya Regional Agricultural Research Station, Sarkanda Farm, Bilaspur (M. P.), India

We conducted multilocation experiments to determine the effect of blue-green algae (BGA) inoculation on rice yields in sandy to clay loam soils in Chhatis-

garh, Madhya Pradesh. Soil pH and available P at different locations are given in Table 1.

BGA was applied alone and in combination with nitrogen fertilizer, and 18 kg P and 12 kg K/ha were applied to all treat-

ments. Kranti, a medium-duration cultivar, was transplanted at 20- × 10-cm spacing. The crop was affected by grasshopper *Hieroglyphus banian* and bacterial blight, and pest control practices were used.

Table 1. Soil pH and available P of experimental soils.

Location	Soil type	Soil pH	Available P (kg/ha)
<i>1981</i>			
Regza	Sandy loam	7.6	16.6
Khoksa	Clay loam	7.8	15.9
Sarkanda	Clay loam	7.4	27.2
<i>1982</i>			
Sarkanda	Clay loam	1.5	15.4

Table 2. Average grain yield of rice as affected by blue-green algae and nitrogen levels.

Treatment (kg/ha)	Grain yield (t/ha)			
	1981			1982
	Regza (sandy loam)	Khoksa (clay loam)	Sarkanda (clay loam)	Sarkanda (clay loam)
Control (no BGA, no fertilizer)	3.0	1.7	2.3	3.9
10 BGA	3.4	2.0	2.7	4.6
20 N	3.3	2.7	3.7	5.2
20 N + 10 BGA	3.7	2.8	3.0	5.9
40 N	3.8	2.6	3.2	5.5
40 N + 10 BGA	3.8	2.8	3.5	6.2
60 N	3.9	2.6	3.9	6.2
60 N + 10 BGA	3.9	2.9	3.9	6.5
CD (0.005)	0.4	0.6	0.3	1.2